

Reproducibility Study: Learning to Generalize in Heterogeneous Federated Networks

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Reproducing the results of a scientific paper in the domain of Data Science can be challenging, as these results are often dependent on a multitude of different factors, such as the exact data, models, parameters, methods and many others. Failing to report some specific detail of the experiment performed can quickly lead to the outcome being non-reproducible.

In this report, we examine a work that proposes a novel federated learning approach, and examine if the information and resources provided are sufficient for re-running the experiment, if the experiment setup is sound and if we can achieve similar results to those reported.

CCS Concepts: • **Computer systems organization** → **Artificial intelligence**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility study, AI, Heterogeneous Federated Learning, Meta Optimization

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1 INTRODUCTION

We have chosen the paper **Learning to Generalize in Heterogeneous Federated Networks** [1] for the reproducibility project in Experiment Design WS2022. The authors propose a novel federated optimization framework, FedMC, that promises to outperform the current state-of-the-art methods.

In Federated Learning, a machine learning model is trained on multiple devices, each having its own local dataset, that train a model locally and exchange model updates with a central coordinator. The central coordinator can then aggregate these updates and send back new information to all clients. This means that data does not need to be sent to a centralized server for training, thus reducing the privacy risks related to the transmission, storage, and analysis of confidential data.

One major challenge in federated learning is that the local datasets may not be representative of the whole population. They can differ in terms of size, class balance, and other features. This property is called statistical heterogeneity. This means that the clients have different goals from each other and different model structures that are optimal for the respective client. FedMC addresses these challenges by using both personalization to optimize the individual client tasks and a meta-critic that allows capturing client-agnostic information.

The aim of our project is to examine the mentioned paper in terms of reproducibility of the results and assess the quality of the experimental setup. The source code, as well as the datasets, are available on GitHub via the following [link](#).

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Dataset	Clients	Samples	Samples per Client	Classes	Base Model
MNIST	100	70 000	700	10	2CNN + 2FC
CIFAR-10	100	60 000	600	10	4CNN + 2FC
CIFAR-100	100	60 000	600	100	4CNN + 2FC
HAR	30	10 269	342.3	6	4CNN + 2FC

Table 1. Model and data-distribution for each of the datasets

2 SETUP

2.1 Overview

The experiments in the paper were conducted on four well-known publicly available datasets. The performance of the proposed method was compared to 8 other federated baselines and a centralized learning approach, where each client trains on the respective local dataset alone, without exchanging any information with a central server. They were compared based on the average accuracy of all individual client test sets. The same models were used for all learning methods. Hyperparameters that are only relevant for a specific method were selected using grid search.

Each experiment was repeated 3 times and for each experiment, the mean accuracy and its standard deviation were reported. Furthermore, t-tests with $p < 0.01$ were conducted to verify if the difference between the proposed method and the best baseline was statistically significant.

Besides the main finding, some additional experiments were conducted, focused on the effects of certain parameters and dataset properties. However, mainly due to computational limitations, we will limit the scope of this project to only reproducing and evaluating the main experiment for the proposed method and one baseline.

2.2 Datasets and Models

There were 4 datasets used for the experiments:

- MNIST - labeled handwritten dataset in image recognition.
- CIFAR-10 - labeled image classification dataset.
- CIFAR-100 - same as CIFAR-10 but with more classes.
- HAR - real-world human activity recognition dataset. The task of the data is to predict the next movement or action.

For the datasets that are not heterogeneous by nature (all but HAR), the data was divided between clients in a non-balanced manner to enforce statistical heterogeneity.

A neural-network-model with multiple convolutional layers and 2 fully connected layers was used for the experiments. The architecture differs slightly depending on the dataset. Firstly, the classification head of the model depends on the number of classes in the dataset and secondly, the MNIST model has two convolutional layers less than the other models. More details are given in Table 1.

The global training parameters, like number of local epochs and learning rate are not set individually for each approach but rather depend on the dataset and are shown in Table 2.

Dataset	lr	lrDecay	batchSize	clientsPerRound	epoch	numRounds
MNIST	0.01	0.99	10	10	5	100
CIFAR-10	0.1	0.99	50	10	5	100
CIFAR-100	0.1	0.99	50	10	5	500
HAR	0.01	0.99	10	20	5	100

Table 2. Global training parameters for each dataset

2.3 Federated Learning Methods and Hyperparameters

The following baselines were considered:

- Stand-alone: locally trained and evaluated models without communications
- Generic federated learning methods:
 - FedAvg
 - FedProx
- Personalized federated learning methods
 - MOCHA
 - FedPer
 - LG-FedAvg
 - Per-FedAvg
 - FedRep
 - FedFomo

The baselines FedProx, LG-FedAvg, FedPer and FedRep and Per-FedAvg all have method-specific hyperparameters that were selected by conducting a grid-search. The values that were considered for this grid-search are reported in the paper. For the proposed method, FedMC, hyperparameter tuning was performed to find the optimal Wasserstein distance coefficient from 0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and critic regularizer weight from 10, 100, 1000.

2.4 Code

The authors of the paper published their code on Github¹. The repository contains some instructions, a requirements file and an example script for running one experiment. Datasets are automatically downloaded, except for HAR, which needs to be downloaded from Google Drive and placed in the correct folder. For the implementation, PyTorch was used and each aggregation method was implemented from scratch.

3 REPRODUCIBILITY ISSUES

While the paper mentions which hyperparameters were considered for the grid search for method-specific parameters, it does not report which ones were finally chosen. Furthermore, there is no information on what the exact setup was for the grid searches. For example, it is not mentioned what data the grid search was performed on, so there is no indication of a validation set, and the repository does not contain any option to specify that part of the training set should be used for validation.

There is some confusion in the description of the choice of model architecture. It is stated that for Cifar10 and MNIST the same architecture was used as in [2], which employed a model with two convolutional layers. Furthermore, for

¹<https://github.com/ECNU-CILAB/FedMC>

157 Cifar100 the same model was used as for Cifar10. However, the table in the paper says that Cifar10 and Cifar100 have 4
158 convolutional layers instead of 2. The code shows that the table is correct and not the textual description.

159 Another issue is the naming of the hyperparameters in the repository. It is difficult to discern which parameter-name
160 corresponds to which parameter, as the naming is not the same as in the paper (or there is some mix-up in the paper).
161 For example, the two parameters for FedMC are described as follows in the repository:

- 162 • mu: "coefficient for balancing cross entropy loss and critic loss" with default value 0.001
- 163 • omega: "coefficient for balancing w-distance loss and gradient penalty loss" with default value 10

164
165 In the paper they are described as:

- 166 • Wasserstein distance coefficient from 0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1
- 167 • Critic regularizer weight from 10, 100, 1000

168 From the description, it seems like omega is the Wasserstein distance coefficient, but from the values the opposite seems
169 more likely. We assumed the latter for our experiments.

170 4 EXPERIMENTS

171 4.1 Our Approach

172 As mentioned above, we only focus on reproducing the results from the main experiment for FedMC and one baseline
173 method. We chose FedAvg as that baseline method, because there are no method-specific hyperparameters for that
174 method that need to be tuned, so we were able to verify if the results are similar when using the exact same parameter
175 setup.

176 For the hyperparameters of FedMC, the default values found in the repository were initially tried, and following that a
177 hyperparameter search for one of the datasets was performed to see if more similar results can be achieved that way. It
178 is important to note that no information is given on how hyperparameter-search was performed in the paper, which
179 is why we had to make a reasonable guess for the setup. We divided the original training set into a training and a
180 validation sets with 80/20 split and performed one run for all combinations of the values given in 2.3 in a grid-search.

181 5 RESULTS

182 The aggregated results of the experiments using the hyperparameters found in the repository for FedMC are shown in
183 Table 3. For all experiments, we found that our results are in the same general range as the reported values. Still, the
184 values of FedAvg on two datasets and of FedMC (with default values) on three datasets have a statistically significant
185 difference to our results based on a two-sample t-test with $\alpha = 0.01$. The first two rows of the table show the results for
186 FedAvg (the baseline method we chose) from the paper and of our experiments. The difference here is surprising, as
187 there are no method-specific hyperparameters for that algorithm, meaning we did not have to resort to using the values
188 that are set in the repository.

189 The next two rows show the results for FedMC reported by the paper and produced by our experiments when using
190 the hyperparameters from the repository. The differences on the MNIST dataset are especially large - FedAvg even
191 outperforms FedMC in our experiment, however, this might be caused by the parameters from the repository being
192 sub-optimal.

193 The last row shows the results of our experiment after performing parameter tuning as described in 4.1 on only the
194 MNIST dataset (parameter tuning was not performed for the other datasets due to computational limitations). It can
195 be seen that, compared to using non-tuned-parameters, there is no longer a statistically significant difference and the

	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	HAR
FedAvg (Reported)	97.66 ± 0.14	52.90 ± 0.65	29.21 ± 0.41	93.45 ± 0.39
FedAvg (Ours)	97.58 ± 0.08	55.23 ± 0.35*	26.54 ± 0.59*	91.80 ± 0.62
FedMC (Reported)	99.51 ± 0.08	87.67 ± 0.11	56.41 ± 0.63	96.14 ± 0.36
FedMC (Ours)	92.84 ± 1.38*	84.74 ± 0.36*	50.44 ± 0.62*	95.06 ± 1.78
FedMC Tuned (Ours)	99.58 ± 0.04	-	-	-

Results with * have a statistically significant difference to reported result on a significance level of 1%

Table 3. Accuracy and Standard Deviation of FedAvg and FedMC

resulting values are very similar to what is reported in the paper. The parameter tuning has shown that the optimal values for FedMC on the validation set for the MNIST dataset are a Wasserstein distance coefficient of 0.00001 and critic regularizer weight of 100.

6 CONCLUSION

The experiment setup described in the paper is solid - a novel approach is compared to eight baselines on four datasets, this process is repeated three times and the mean and standard deviation of the resulting accuracy-values are reported and tested for statistical significance using t-tests with a 0.01 confidence interval.

The code is available in a Github repository and runs without issues. Furthermore, the datasets are either loaded directly in the code or instructions are available for downloading them.

Information on models used, training parameters and parameters for the federated learning (i.e Samples per Client, Number of Clients, ...) are provided. For approaches that require hyperparameters, the considered parameters for a grid-search are stated.

However, the paper fails to list the hyperparameters that were eventually chosen as a result of the hyperparameter tuning. Also, there is no information given on how the parameter tuning was performed and there is no mention of a validation set. In addition, the descriptions of the hyperparameters for FedMC in the paper and in the repository do not match and it seems they were mixed up, making it less clear which values should be considered for the parameter tuning. Lastly, there is some confusion on the number of convolutional layers that are used for the models. In particular, there is a small contradiction between the textual description in the paper and the code in the repository.

The results of our experiments are roughly on the same scale as the results given in the paper. However, there are some statistically significant difference for which we have no explanation. In particular, FedAvg takes no specific hyperparameters but still gets significantly different results compared to what is reported.

For FedMC, we also achieve distinct results when we use the hyperparameters from the repository (which differ from the ones that result from tuning), but this could be explained by the non-optimal parameters.

MNIST is the only dataset, for which we performed hyperparameter tuning using our own tuning setup as opposed to using the parameters from the repository, since none was specified in the paper. Here, we obtain results that much more closely resemble the numbers reported in the papers. Unfortunately, we could not do this hyperparameter-search for all datasets due to limited computing resources.

In conclusion, it can be said that the paper is largely reproducible. The optimal hyperparameters are an important piece of information that is missing from the paper. Nevertheless, the rest of the experiment is mostly described in sufficient details and the provided code is functional.

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A APPENDIX

Table 4 shows the non-aggregated accuracy of the three runs of each experiment with default parameters on the test set. Table 5 shows the accuracy for different parameter combinations of FedMC on the MNIST validation set with seed 102. Table 6 shows the accuracy of FedMC with optimal parameters on the MNIST test set.

Seed	MNIST		CIFAR10		CIFAR100		HAR	
	FedAvg	FedMC	FedAvg	FedMC	FedAvg	FedMC	FedAvg	FedMC
7	0.9759	0.9441	0.5532	0.8460	0.2701	0.5108	0.9247	0.9583
12	0.9766	0.9230	0.5552	0.8448	0.2673	0.5040	0.9170	0.9632
52	0.9750	0.9181	0.5484	0.8515	0.2587	0.4984	0.9124	0.9302
Mean	0.9758	0.9284	0.5523	0.8474	0.2654	0.5044	0.9180	0.9506
Standard Div.	0.0008	0.0138	0.0035	0.0036	0.0059	0.0062	0.0062	0.0178

Table 4. Full Experiment Accuracy Results with Default Values

	$\mu=0.1$	$\mu=0.01$	$\mu=0.001$	$\mu=0.0001$	$\mu=0.00001$
$\omega=10$	0.9605	0.9635	0.9179	0.9924	0.9925
$\omega=100$	0.9669	0.9375	0.8746	0.992	0.9926
$\omega=1000$	0.971	0.7383	0.8505	0.9917	0.9925

Table 5. FedMC Accuracy on Validation Set for Finetuning

MNIST - Tuned	
Seed	FedMC
7	0.9958
12	0.9962
52	0.9954
Mean	0.9958
Standard Div.	0.0004

Table 6. Optimal FedMC Accuracy on Test Set

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